

Studies on Hexammine Cobaltic Sulphate. Part II.

BY PULIN BIHARI SARKAR AND TARA PRASAD BARAT.

Like the alkali sulphates, hexammine cobaltic sulphate combines with acids to give rise to acid salts. These acid salts have been investigated by several workers and three compounds belonging to this class have so far been mentioned. Unfortunately, the authors gave no details of their preparations. They are as follows:—

(i) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (Jørgensen, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1888, 17, 458).

(ii) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (Benrath and Würzberg, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 135, 229).

(iii) $2\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3\} \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Klobb, *Bull. Soc. franc. Min.*, 24, 313).

All the three compounds form well defined crystals. The first and the third compounds were known from a long time, the identity of the second being lately established by Benrath and Würzberg (*loc. cit.*) who, at the same time, threw doubt on the existence of the last one. Contradictory statements as regards the existence of the acid salts require the matter to be re-investigated. Accordingly, the equilibrium study has been extended to the case of these acid salts, as a result of which it has been definitely established that hexammine cobaltic sulphate forms three and only three acid salts with sulphuric acid. Their mode of formation and range of stability have been determined.

The Ternary System, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ — H_2SO_4 —Water at 35°.

The solubility of hexammine cobaltic sulphate in sulphuric acid at different concentrations have been determined, the equilibrium being studied at 35°. Pure hexammine cobaltic sulphate was prepared by the method used in the previous investigation. The cobalt in solution was estimated by electrolytic method observing the precautions stated in Part I. The free sulphuric acid was determined

by titrating with standard alkali solution using silver nitrate as an indicator. Later on, the method of conductometric titration for estimating the free acid in these acid salts was employed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A weighed quantity of the salt was placed in a 100 c.c. bottle, and about 75 c. c. of the standard acid solution added. The contents of the bottle were slightly warmed by placing in a water-bath at 60° . The bottle was vigorously shaken in a mechanical shaker, and placed in a thermostat regulated at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. During this time a solid phase or phases separated out. After the solid phase had been allowed to settle, about 10 c. c. of the clear solution was pipetted off, weighed and analysed. When the equilibrium had attained, the solid phase was separated from the liquid by filtering on a small Buchner funnel, a funnel provided with a silica bed being used for filtering solutions containing a high concentration of sulphuric acid. The solid salts obtained were often pasty due to the adhering acid solution which could not be completely removed by draining. The salt was nearly dried by pressing within the folds of a blotting paper several times and analysed.

FIG. 1.

Percentage of acid.	G. of Co per 100 g. of aqueous solution.	Typical analysis of corresponding solid phases.			Remarks on solid phases.
		% Co	% SO ₄ (total)	% H ₂ SO ₄	
0	0.4013	16.82	40.68	—	} Pure [Co(NH ₃) ₆] ₂ (SO ₄) ₃
0.75	0.7044	—	—	—	
1.5	1.1121	16.94	41.37	Minute traces.	
2	1.2806	17	41.28	"	
2.3	1.2063	16.69	54.07	14.07	
3	1.0911	—	—	—	} First acid salt
5	0.8103	16.72	54.46	18.95	
7.5	0.7540	—	—	—	
10	0.7472	—	—	—	
15	0.7827	16.84	54.59	18.98	
17.1	0.7196	13.95	54.86	22.78	
20	0.5217	—	—	—	
25	0.2590	—	—	—	
30	0.1632	—	—	—	
35	0.1141	18.57	54.29	22.85	
40	0.1125	—	—	—	} Second acid salt.
45.1	0.1162	—	—	—	
50	0.1760	13.53	54.78	22.28	
55	0.5045	—	—	—	
60	0.4629	13.55	55.15	22.68	
61	0.4037	12.41	55.65	26.23	} Third acid salt.
62	0.3208	—	—	—	
65	0.1980	—	—	—	
70	0.0984	12.59	55.43	26.19	
75	0.0512	—	—	—	
80	0.0415	—	—	—	

These results have been graphically represented (Fig. 1). The abscissa represents the strength of sulphuric acid, while the ordinate

shows the number of grams of cobalt dissolved in 100 g. of aqueous solution. The solubility of the neutral salt in 0 per cent. acid (*i.e.* pure water) is represented by the point (*a*). The solubility rises with an increase in acid concentration until about 2.1% is reached, after which it gradually diminishes reaching a minimum at (*c*). The maximum (*b*), therefore, represents the first transition point. The cobalt content of the solution again increased with an increase in the acid concentration until a second maximum point (*d*) is reached. This represents a second maximum point and corresponds to about 16.1% of acid. The curve after passing through a third minimum (*e*) again rises with an increase in acid strength, until a third transition point (*f*) is reached. This point corresponds to about 60.3% of acid. After this, the curve gradually slopes down. The solubility determinations have been carried out for solutions of sulphuric acid, the strength varying from 0—80%. After this, the cobalt in solution was found to be too small for accurate analysis.

The Compounds of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ with Sulphuric Acid.

(1) The *first acid salt* has been obtained by crystallising $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ from sulphuric acid solutions whose strength varies from 2.1 to 16.1 per cent. The salt crystallises in pale yellow shining crystals, which do not contain any water of crystallisation. It is freely soluble in water, the solutions being strongly acid. The salt decomposes when heated to 130°. (Found: Co, 16.56; total SO_4 , 53.86; H_2SO_4 , 13.99. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ requires Co, 16.66; total SO_4 , 54.23; H_2SO_4 , 13.84 per cent.)

(2) The *second acid salt* has been obtained by crystallising the mother substance from dilute sulphuric acid solutions containing 16.1—60.3 per cent. sulphuric acid. It crystallises in brownish red crystals which are freely soluble in water. The air-dried product on analysis gave results which were different from those given by Benrath and Würzberg (*loc. cit.*) the results being considerably low in each case. It was, therefore, inferred that the salt contains water of crystallisation as well. In order to verify the limit of stability of the attached water molecules, the ordinary product was dried in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid for a week, until it was of constant weight. By this treatment the salt neither changed in colour, nor lost its characteristic crystalline appearance. It was then analysed and the results were found to agree with those obtained

previously from the air-dried sample. Finally a weighed quantity of the air-dried product was dehydrated in a thermostat at different temperatures, up to 110°. All these evidences, therefore, lead to the conclusion that the compound invariably contains water of crystallisation, which is very firmly held. The water content agrees with the formula $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The salt decomposes and turns purple when heated to 125°. (Found: H_2O , 8.12; Co, 13.51; total SO_4 , 54.8; H_2SO_4 , 22.5. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 8.2; Co, 13.44; total SO_4 , 54.7; H_2SO_4 , 22.33 per cent.).

(3) The *third acid salt* has been obtained by crystallising $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ from sulphuric acid solutions whose strength exceeds 60.3 per cent. The salt forms pale yellow rhombic octahedra. It is slightly hygroscopic, and gains in weight if left for any length of time in air. On gradual heating the hydrated salt gives up its water of crystallisation until the anhydrous salt decomposes at about 125°. (Found: Co, 12.41; total SO_4 , 55.4; H_2SO_4 , 26.1; H_2O , 9.42. $2\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3\} \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 12.48; total SO_4 , 55.88; H_2SO_4 , 26; H_2O , 9.52 per cent.).

Conductometric Titration of Acid Salts with Standard Baryta Solution.

Conductivity was determined by Kohlrausch's method.

The conductivity, $C = 1/R \times a/(100-a)$

where R = standard resistance and a = bridge readings.

R being constant, the quantity actually measured was $a/(100-a)$.

This is proportional to the conductivity and was plotted against the volume of reagent added.

A weighed quantity of the salt was dissolved in water so that the strengths of the acid solutions were of the order of $N/400$ — $N/500$.

The standard baryta solution was added from a micro-burette graduated to 0.01 c.c. the open ends being closed by rubber tubing carrying small soda-lime tubes, for protecting the baryta from the action of carbon dioxide of the air. The conductivity of the solution was first measured. The reagent was then added and the conductivity again measured. The values were then plotted against the amount of reagent added, the composition of the salt being determined from the break in the curve.

The curves obtained are of the form shown in Figure 2. At first, the conductivity was very high, but it gradually diminished on neutralising the free acid. At a point, the conductivity was minimum, which indicates the exact neutralisation point. The

FIG. 2.

diminution of conductivity is due to the removal of hydrogen and SO_4 -ions, hydrogen being most mobile of all ions. On further addition of the reagent, the conductivity again increases due to the replacement of SO_4 ions by OH -ions, the latter being most mobile next to hydron. The second break in the curve is obtained when all the SO_4 -ions are precipitated. The conductivity increases very slowly due to the increase in the concentration of both OH - and Ba -ions.

Results.

Titration of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (Fig. 2, Curve I).

Substance taken = 0.0795 g.

C.c. of baryta solution added.	Conductivity.	C.c. of baryta solution added.	Conductivity.
0	1.15	3.5	0.64
0.4	0.92	4.0	0.71
0.8	0.78	4.5	0.78
1.1	0.68	5.0	0.832
1.3	0.55	5.5	0.901
1.5	0.47	6.1	1.00
1.7	0.41	6.4	1.05
1.9	0.44	6.8	1.15
2.1	0.46	7.3	1.29
2.5	0.51	7.8	1.40
3.0	0.58		

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Volume of baryta solution required to neutralise $H_2SO_4(A_1)$
= 1.66 c.c.

Volume of baryta solution required to precipitate sulphate
($B_1 - A_1$) = 4.62 c.c.

Strength of the baryta solution = 0.14N.

(Found: H_2SO_4 , 14.21; SO_4 , 39.12. $[Co(NH_3)_6]_2(SO_4)_3$, H_2SO_4
requires H_2SO_4 , 13.85; SO_4 , 40.07 per cent.).

Titration of $[Co(NH_3)_6]_2(SO_4)_3 \cdot 2H_2SO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ (Fig. 2, Curve II).

Substance taken = 0.0480 g.

C.c. of baryta solution added.	Conductivity.	C.c. of baryta solution added.	Conductivity.
0	1.62	2.4	0.565
0.4	1.27	2.9	0.71
0.8	0.98	3.4	0.88
1.1	0.74	3.7	0.97
1.3	0.55	4.0	1.06
1.5	0.43	4.3	1.18
1.7	0.35	4.7	1.35
1.9	0.43	5.1	1.55

Volume of baryta solution required to neutralise free $H_2SO_4(A_2)$
= 1.6 c.c.

Volume of baryta solution required to precipitate $SO_4(B_2 - A_2)$
= 2.43 c.c.

Strength of baryta solution = 0.14N.

(Found: H_2SO_4 , 22.78; SO_4 , 33.9. $[Co(NH_3)_6]_2(SO_4)_3$, $2H_2SO_4$,
 $4H_2O$ requires H_2SO_4 , 22.3; SO_4 , 32.8 per cent.).

Titration of $2\{[Co(NH_3)_6]_2(SO_4)_3\} \cdot 5H_2SO_4 \cdot 10H_2O$ (Fig. 2, Curve III)

Substance taken = 0.0511 g.

C.c. of baryta solution added.	Conductivity.	C.c. of baryta solution added.	Conductivity.
0	1.85	2.6	0.38
0.4	1.535	3.0	0.41
0.7	1.23	3.6	0.48
1.0	1.08	4.0	0.52
1.4	0.78	4.3	0.55
1.7	0.55	4.6	0.60
1.9	0.40	5.1	0.71
2.1	0.33	5.6	0.80
2.3	0.35	6.1	0.88

Volume of baryta solution required to neutralise free $H_2SO_4(A_3)$
= 1.98 c.c.

Volume of baryta solution required to precipitate SO_4 ($B_3 - A_3$) = 2.35 c.c.

Strength of the baryta solution = 0.14N.

(Found: H_2SO_4 , 26.4; SO_4 , 80.88. $2\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3\}$, $5\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$, $10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2SO_4 , 25.9; SO_4 , 80.05 per cent.).

The results obtained show a difference from 1–3 per cent. with those obtained from theoretical calculations. These are due to—

(a) An increase of volume which should be avoided as far as possible, for, the conductivity measurements are related to the proportion of the ions contained in the total volume of the solution. Hence the original solution used was very dilute and the titrating reagent as strong as possible.

(b) The rise of temperature which, for 1° , increases the conductivity by 2 per cent. To avoid a sudden fluctuation of temperature, the beaker containing the solution was placed within a larger vessel containing water, the latter serving the purpose of a thermostat.

Summary.

From a supersaturated solution of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ in sulphuric acid the following phases will crystallise out at 35° .

(1) Pure $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ if the acid concentration be less than 2.1 per cent.

(2) If the acid concentration lies between 2.1 and 16.1 per cent. the mother substance is quantitatively transformed into the first acid salt.

(3) The second acid salt can be obtained by crystallising the mother substance from sulphuric acid solutions whose strength lies between 16.1 and 60.3 per cent. Contrary to the statements of Benrath and Würzberg (*loc. cit.*), the second acid salt is a tetrahydrated product.

(4) If the acid concentration exceeds 60.3 per cent. the third acid salt is obtained.